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Status of ICT Resources in the Schools: Basis for Utilization and Procurement Plans

Nel Rusty T. Tamayo*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to comprehensively examine the status of ICT resources in Masbate province's third congressional elementary and secondary district public schools, utilizing a mixed-methods approach. The quantitative aspect involved data collection from 102 school heads and ICT coordinators, while the qualitative component focused on insights gathered solely from school principals. A survey checklist was designed to assess the availability, functionality, and sufficiency of ICT resources, and statistical methods such as rank order, frequency, and a Likert scale were employed for interpretation. Qualitative data obtained through thematic analysis of interviews with school principals highlighted specific struggles and challenges faced by the schools. Findings indicated that there is a scarcity of ICT resources in third-district schools, and the existing resources are not fully functional or sufficient. Additional challenges, supported by qualitative findings, include an undersupply of ICT resources, untrained teachers, the unavailability of maintenance personnel, and unstable internet connectivity. These identified challenges underscored the need for a comprehensive approach to addressing ICT-related issues in the third district schools. In conclusion, the study's findings revealed a significant gap in the availability, functionality, and sufficiency of ICT resources in the third congressional district. To address these issues, the study proposed several recommendations based on its findings. Firstly, the department is encouraged to enhance intervention strategies related to all-inclusive procurement services. The study also suggested that the department will allocate funds for extra personnel to enhance the serviceability of ICT resources. Furthermore, providing additional training for teachers in utilizing ICT for classroom instruction was recommended. Lastly, utilization and procurement plans were recommended to serve as augmented solutions to improve the overall status of ICT in these schools and address the identified challenges for enhancing the quality of education.

Keywords: *third-district schools, ICT resources, mixed methods approach, availability, functionality, sufficiency*

Introduction

Digital literacy is highly and favorably associated with effective and positive educational characteristics. Goldhaber et al. (2021) came to the same result as Phutela and Dwivedi (2019), who found that ICT improves self-responsibility, independent learning, and learning maturity.

Ahmadi (2018) also analyzed how technology facilitates communication between teachers and students. Hence, it is more motivating for students to effectively learn a foreign language when the input and output are clear and understandable, the learning and teaching process is more student-centered, the students' autonomy and self-confidence are encouraged, and they feel more confident.

Similar study in the educational system of the Philippines; students' mastery of every competency had increased as a result of the integration of ICT components; ICT materials were tailored to the needs of the learners and their intellectual capacity, making the learning simple to fully comprehend (Falqueza, 2019).

Although ICT has many benefits for educational learning, it also has some drawbacks that require attention for better school-ICT integration. Murithi and Yoo (2021) concluded that ICT facilities, such as projectors, tablets, student PCs, and other aiding equipment, were insufficient. Teachers should be given computers so they can easily access resources and get ready for technology integration. This will lessen the need for computer technicians in schools by acquainting teachers with computer hardware and software. Tomaro & Mutiarin (2018) highlighted in their study that despite ICT being taught in schools, there are several issues threatening the effectiveness of technological education among Filipino youths. Infrastructure and facilities (computers, etc.), human resources (limited teacher training, low teacher motivation, and low technological knowledge), and thirdly, the requirement for a technological leader who would play a crucial role in successfully integrating ICT in the curriculum.

This study is instigated for a sounding comprehension of ICT resource status and utilization in Masbate province, in particular the third congressional district public schools as Capuno et al. (2022) suggested that digital citizenship instruction be included in schools and that increased school participation is required to produce globally responsible digital citizens. A timely research project also purposely engendered for the crafting of utilization and procurement plans to contribute to the sustainable utilization and policy strengthening of the department's ICT procurement and operation matters.

Primarily, the study is focused on the schools' ICT resource sufficiency and functionality levels under its status, ICT resource availability, and the challenges and struggles encountered. School heads were the primary respondents to the study, though others made an endorsement to an ICT coordinator to fill out the survey checklist provided. Additionally, selected school principals were interviewed, vocally describing the struggles and challenges they encountered.

Research Questions

This study is meant to assess the status of ICT resources in the third congressional district of Masbate Province. Specifically, it was conducted to answer the following questions:

1. What are the ICT resources available in the school?
2. What is the status of ICT resources in terms of functionality?
3. What is the status of ICT resources in terms of sufficiency?
4. What are the struggles and challenges of the school heads in managing ICT resources?
5. What possible output can be proposed to improve the management of ICT utilization?

Methodology

Research Design

This research includes quantitative method and a qualitative method. Purposely, these methods are envisioned to illustrate the availability, status of utilization in terms of functionality and sufficiency, and struggles and challenges encountered in the utilization of ICT resources in the Masbate province's third congressional district public schools.

The quantitative method interprets the ICT resource availability and status in terms of functionality and sufficiency, whereas the qualitative method interprets the struggles and challenges the school is encountering in ICT.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the school heads or ICT coordinators in both elementary and secondary public schools. The population was chosen at random to collect quantitative data, with consideration given to the following insistences: the respondents are more likely to be elementary school heads or ICT coordinators than secondary school heads; the respondents are more openly available for immediate retrieval; and their respective schools have easy access for travel purposes. Qualifications were observed as well for the qualitative data gathering, which is solely limited to principal items, which contain one (1) principal from both elementary and secondary schools in each individual municipality.

In this study, the researcher employed purposive random sampling for quantitative data gathering, wherein all respondents in the third district public schools were equally given opportunities to participate in the study.

Instrument

A self-made survey checklist was employed as the quantitative research tool in this study to collect data. Made conscientiously in three main columns stressing availability through rank order, functionality and sufficiency thru frequency count and Likert scale. The survey checklist was checked by the adviser and other experts for its quality assurance. Semi-structured interviews were employed as a qualitative research tool using thematic analysis. The researcher formulated a semi-structured interview for each of the responding principals. There are five set of questions for the respondents but the answers were thematically analyzed only those citing the struggles and challenges they encountered about the status of ICT.

The researcher used three (3) statistical methods: rank order on available ICT resource domains, frequency distribution and Likert scale to determine the utilization status of ICT resources in terms of functionality and sufficiency, and thematic analysis to further explore the struggles and challenges given by the respondent principals.

Rank order is used to clarify available ICT resource in each of the three (3) different ICT domains that include hardware, software and facilities. Used is a four-column table contains rank, available ICT resources, number of available and not available ICT resource.

Frequency interprets the utilization in terms of functionality and sufficiency identifying its level among each of the ICT domains.

Likert Scale. This tool is used to interpret the responses on the levels of functionality and sufficiency of the three (3) ICT domains under its utilization status by means of a 4 point-value system.

Thematic Analysis. In this tool, there are five different sets of questions the researcher personally made, which served as guide during the interviews and were transcribed for the analysis afterward.

The gathered qualitative data about struggles and challenges among the respondents was comprehended from a four-column transcription comprising questions, responses, formulated meaning, and themes. The responses about struggles and challenges were coded, which generated themes following the six steps; familiarization of data, initial coding, generating themes, validity and reliability of themes, defining and naming themes, and interpretation and reporting.

This thematic methodology was attributed to Braun & Clarke (2006) as describe in Xu & Zammit (2020) that extends, a theme is a particular sequence that was identified and has pattern interpretations throughout the data set. It includes some key information about the data in respect to the study objectives.

Results and Discussion

Availability of ICT Resources in Schools

In ICT hardware domain, among the twenty-one (21) numbered equipment and tool in the schools as mentioned in table 1a, only eight (8) of which are highly available, this was challenged with the findings of Irmayani et al. (2022) that lacked of ICT infrastructure, insufficient financing for ICT programs, lack of ICT personnel will leave a constraint in ICT management. Related findings also have been made by Jegede (2020) that lack of ICT resource and bad nature services causes ICT constrains.

As to the ICT software domain, seven different applications of the eighteen total listed are available as appeared in Table 1b, meaning third district schools only cater to the basic application ones, and those may be of the lighter storage size in terms of installation capacity. However, the findings in this domain is some way confronted by the feasible technology involvement to education from Cheng (2012) as mentioned in the study of Merillo & Domingo (2019) that social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter, blogs, wikis, and instant messaging can enhance instruction and learning outside the school by enabling students to use avenue of interaction that is no longer restricted to the school environment that “facilitate collaborative discussion, exchange of opinions, and critical thinking”.

Table 1.1. *Availability of Hardware Domain*

<i>ICT Tool or Equipment</i>	<i>Frequency (Availability)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Printer (3in1)	102	1
Printer	24	
Television	91	2
Flash Drives	83	3
Laptop	79	4
Projector	77	5
Desktop Computer Set	74	6
Laminating Machine	59	7
Portable Speaker	56	8
Hard Drives	41	9
Tablet	38	10
Headphones/ Earphones	34	11
Netbook	34	12
Android Phone	27	13
Book Binding Machine	25	14
Photocopier	24	15
Scanner	20	16
Mobile Phone	11	17
CD/DVD Player	10	18
Digital Camera	7	19
iPhone	0	20
Fax Machines	0	21

Table 1.2. *Availability of Software Domain*

<i>Software Component</i>	<i>Frequency (Available)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
School records' Database System (LIS)	102	1
MS Word	84	3
MS Excel	84	3
MS PowerPoint	84	3
LR portals/ LRMS	79	5.5
Facebook /Messenger	79	5.5
YouTube	76	7
MS Publisher	42	9.5
Google classroom	42	9.5
Google meet	42	9.5
Zoom	42	9.5
MS Access	33	12
Adobe Photoshop	30	13
Instagram	28	14
Canva App	22	15

Twitter	20	16
AutoCAD	0	17
Corel Draw	0	18

Table 1.3 contains ICT facilities, the last of the three domains in the ICT availability resource. It is mainly stated in the table that all responding schools have access to power supply, where Masbate Electric Cooperative (MASELCO) is the lone provider. Other schools have backup power like solar and generator sets, whereas others do not. Saying that the internet is unstable among schools, the piso Wi-Fi innovations aided commonly upon the internet connectivity issue. Schools in the third district mostly do not have access to the internet, or if they do, the internet speed is also a concern. The majority of the public schools as well do not have computer laboratories, including audio-video rooms (AVR), though it is evident that mini or modified computer labs are the alternatives. Mini/Modified Computer Labs are enhanced, shared, or temporary buildings that serve as housing for computer equipment present in the schools. Additionally, among the 3rd district schools, only one has a CCTV camera, and the entire school does not have an e-library.

Table 1.3. Availability of ICT Facility Domain

<i>ICT facilities</i>	<i>Frequency (Available) Rank</i>	
Power Source		
Masbate Electric Corporation (MASELCO)	102	1
Generator Set	35	
Solar Power	20	
Wi-Fi Hotspots area (Piso Net)	46	2
Mini/Modified Computer Laboratory	40	3
Wireless Internet connectivity (Data subscription)		4
Smart	39	
Globe	23	
Computer Laboratory	28	5
Wired Internet connectivity		
PLDT	22	6
Audio/Video Room	14	7
Tele conferencing room/area	3	8
CCTV cameras across campus, classrooms and offices	1	9
E-Library	0	10

Status of ICT Resources in Schools in Terms of Functionality

Table 2. General Status of ICT Resources in Terms of Functionality

<i>ICT Resources</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
ICT Hardware	1.93	Somewhat Functional
ICT Software	1.97	Somewhat Functional
ICT Facility	2.44	Somewhat Functional
General Weighted Mean	2.13	Somewhat Functional

The distinct three (3) ICT resource domain weighted mean was taken from the total weighted mean of each single ICT resource, shown in table 2. Weighted mean in terms of ICT functionality status is interpreted generally as somewhat functional having 2.13 weighted mean, this comprise the weighted mean of ICT hardware, software and facility.

These results demonstrate the need for teachers' ICT-related beliefs, attitudes, and expertise to be considered aside from implementing initial investment of school ICT highly functional infrastructures. Also, Tomaro & Mutiarin (2018) posits, Philippine schools' facilities and technological resources were insufficient for use in the classroom, widely stating that it hinders students from becoming computer literate and only widens the digital gap between urban and rural schoolchildren.

Generally concluded that there is a low functionality level among ICT resources that it would cause a low ICT practices among schools. Both teachers and students cannot fully enhance the skills development relating to ICT.

Status of ICT Resources in Schools in Terms of Sufficiency

Demonstrated in table 3 the general weighted mean of each individual ICT resource that was taken from the weighted mean of each three ICT resource domain covering ICT tool or equipment, software, and facility which generally interpreted as not sufficient in terms of ICT sufficiency status.

Table 3. *General Status of ICT Resources in Terms of Sufficiency*

<i>ICT Resources</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
ICT Hardware	1.66	Not Sufficient
ICT Software	1.86	Somewhat Sufficient
ICT Facility	1.74	Not Sufficient
General Weighted Mean	1.75	Not Sufficient

Majority of the ICT domain in sufficiency have the low levels respectively, low level of ICT sufficiency slows down the process of technological competitiveness among teachers and students. This also claims that despite the government efforts of ICT resource enhancement, additional of personnel or teacher trainings, strengthening of ICT capability and investment, as cited in: DepEd Computerization Program and DepEd Internet Connectivity Program - DCP/DICP, de Dios (2016), and DepEd order 78 series 2010 – Department of Education (2010), there are lot of ICT resources to be given attention yet so far in terms of procurement, maintenance, or upgrades.

Struggles and Challenges Encountered in the Management of ICT Resources in Schools

Responses of the school principals were themed as they asked about the struggles and challenges they encountered in ICT resource management. From the question, there are four extracted themes and these are; Undersupply of ICT Resources, Untrained ICT Teachers; and Unavailable Maintenance Personnel and Procedures; lastly, Unstable Internet Connectivity.

Undersupply of ICT Resources

Among the coded responses, findings revealed that an undersupply of ICT resources is evident among the third district schools. School principals voiced that the pressing issue in ICT is a dearth of hardware, equipment, and tools—the same problem they faced is the absence or lack of ICT building facilities. “Limitation pa din an usad sa mga challenges like, not all teachers, not all classrooms have android televisions, other teachers as well don’t have laptops. Others are asking, requesting, pero dili tanan, dili tanan gayud... Kon maka provide an school, dili inan... Individual at the same time...” (Limitation is still one of the challenges, like the fact that not all teachers and classrooms have Android televisions and other teachers as well don’t have laptops. Others are asking and requesting, but cannot be accommodated all at the same time) Respondent 9.

Department of Education (DepEd) will really have to take additional procurement sets of supplies relating to ICT domains; may it be hardware, software or facility. The validated responses have accepted the like conclusion of Masegenya & Mwila (2023) that there is limited use of ICT in record keeping in public Tanzanian secondary schools due to poor ICT infrastructure, a lack of ICT-trained employees, and a lack of funding for overall maintenance and administration of Information-related applications. There is a need to update, acquire, and use specific ICT resources in order to support a highly competitive learner and better ICT education integration because of the limitations in ICT resources that the data from this study have shown, and if they persist, ICT education integration can impede the development of any learner.

Untrained ICT Teachers

Another extracted theme from the interview is that there were teachers and ICT personnel who do not have trainings and seminars related to ICT classroom teaching and maintenance. ICT resources in schools needing maintenance are not immediately attended due to the absence of ICT maintenance personnel. Also revealed in the interview that teachers including school heads in the age bracket of 50s to 60s need more trainings related to ICT. “Our school met difficulties in using ICT resources most especially those teachers who are above 50s and 60s including the principal. Our learnings in the use of computers were so limited only, so we need the assistance of the young generation to cope up some online reports and other teaching materials in the online system”. Respondent 4.

Trainings are to be taken into consideration upon ICT improvement, as the relative conclusion by Cebuano (2019) in her study that teachers over the age of 50 may need additional training in using ICT in the classroom, and the procurement of ICT facilities and equipment must be carefully considered for greater incorporation into students' learning. Additionally, another asserted finding that the Longer ICT trainings for teachers improved and developed, a better mindset toward integrating ICT inside the classroom (Saprikis, et al. 2019). From the findings, this implies that additional ICT trainings and seminars will provide additional practical learning among teachers in ICT classroom instruction and maintenance abilities.

Unavailable Maintenance Personnel and Procedures

Further extracted response is that there are unavailable school-based maintenance personnel and the maintenance procedures are not applied in an ICT resource respectively. Principals were loud on their stand that servicing is really one method to save certain ICT resources from trouble. This finding was accepted the same proposition from a Nigerian study that governments and ICT resources used in classrooms should be supported, funded, and purchased by interested parties, the basic education boards and ministries should provide special budget devoted to the supply, utilization, and maintenance of the ICT infrastructure (Osiesi et al. 2022). “Sana the government, specially the DepEd will allocate fund for the maintenance, Inan.. Inan sinda na an mag hatag sin supply. Immediately if there are cases... may na sira... Inan mga pang-maintain san mga gamit. Sin ada na tani... Tagaan nalang kita kag sana inan ihahatag,

inan mga ma ayu na klase na computer kay seldom gayud ina an government naga hatag sin the best na computers. Quality sana...” (Hopefully, the government specially the DepEd will allocate fund for the maintenance, like they will really give us supply immediately when there is troubled ICT equipment. In addition, they would also hopefully give us a quality equipment because seldom that the government gives the best quality computers.) Respondent 8.

The findings imply longevity of ICT resources are to be observed when they are taken with the utmost care. Maintenance and maintaining procedures are the key measures for the ICT resource to be saved from disorder.

Unstable Internet Connectivity

The last extracted response among the struggles and challenges as principals are interviewed, is that, unstable of internet connectivity among the public schools. Slow internet connectivity among schools are observe and other schools also do not have direct access to the internet due to signal absence. This finding was also reflected in the previous statement of the problem regarding availability, that only 46 in the entire third district schools only have the connection to internet among 102 respondents through Wi-Fi hotspot area. The highest availability frequency of internet connection acquisition among wireless (e.g. globe and smart) and wired connection (e.g. PLDT and others). “The power interruptions, the poor electric supply that cannot cater all the school’s consumption and no internet signal, even text signal is not available.” Respondent 1

Internet connection has then an advantage for learners however attention and care have to be taken into action for a better value may cause the learners, that the findings of the study agreed to the study’s results from Affum (2022), that the internet significantly improves outcomes for learning. Nonetheless, there are a number of negative consequences that may result in learners losing ground in their academic performance. They must set time limits for themselves when utilizing the technology in order to achieve learning objectives. Internet connectivity when operated fairly among schools would bring learners and teachers strong connection between highly digital classroom instruction and would bring ease on working tasks online instead of extending extra hours outside school’s obligation for an online related task due to its absence or unstable school internet connectivity.

Proposed Output of the Study

Considering all the data from quantitative and qualitative interpretation, evidently revealed that third congressional elementary and secondary public schools in Masbate Province generally struggled and challenged as to status of ICT. Hence, the researcher formulated an output concerning utilization and procurement plans that can be used for procurement and utilization purposes tending a guide to the teachers, school heads, planning and procurement officer or anyone concerned.

It is a self-devised plan having two (2) types of document, one contains the utilization plans and the other contains procurement plan. Utilization plan involves school-based activities, purposes and target to be initiated as directly addressed for approval from the school head and schools’ division superintendent, school head as the recommending approval person and superintendent as the approving person authority. Procurement plan is a template adopted from the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) that DepEd is also legally using when procuring goods and services.

There are two (2) crafting bases this plan involves, taken from the findings of the study: those available ICT resources in the schools are to be inventoried and subject to the utilization plans and procedures, while those unavailable resources are the basis for school or division-based procurement. The procurement proposal is to be given to the planning and procurement officer as a basis for possible procurement procedures. This covers three-year period of implementation starting year 2023 up until year 2026 that may be presented in each school learning action cell (SLAC), educational forums, educational ICT related trainings and seminars or a copy to be handed to the division planning and procurement officer.

Conclusions

Five conclusions were drawn based from the findings of the study on the entire status of ICT resources. First and foremost, ICT education integration can hinder any learner’s development and that there is a need to update, procure, and utilize certain ICT resources for a high delivery ICT teaching and a better ICT education integration. Second, low functionality level among ICT resources would cause a low ICT related practices among schools. Both teachers and students cannot fully enhance the skills development concerning ICT. Third, low level of ICT sufficiency slows down the process of technological competitiveness among teachers and students. Fourth, ICT struggles and challenges are the reasons of hindrances to any learner’s ICT skill development; additional ICT trainings and seminars will provide additional practical learning among teachers in ICT classroom instruction and maintenance abilities; longevity of ICT resources when a well maintenance is observed; internet connectivity when operated fairly among schools would bring learners and teachers strong connection between highly digital classroom instruction and would bring ease on working tasks online. Fifth, outputs about utilization and procurement plans can be used for ICT resource procurement and utilization processes serving as a guide to the teachers, school heads, planning and procurement officer or anyone concerned.

References

Affum, M. Q. (2022, July 1). Effect of ICT on the financial achievements of Atwima Kwanwoma rural bank, Ashanti region. *International Journal of Computing Programming and Database Management*. <https://doi.org/10.33545/27076636.2022.v3.i2a.58>

- Ahmadi, M. R. (2018, June 20). The Use of Technology in English Language Learning: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 3(2), 8. <https://doi.org/10.29252/ijree.3.2.115>
- Capuno, R., Suson, R., Suladay, D., Arnaiz, V., Villarin, I. & Jungoy, E. (2022). Digital citizenship in education and its implication. *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues*. 14(2), 426-437. <https://doi.org/10.18844/wjet.v14i2.6952>
- Cebuano, N. (2019, March). ICT utilization: Cawayan West District Teachers' Experience. In Unpublished Master's Thesis. Dr. Emilio B. Espinosa Sr. Memorial State College of Agriculture and Technology.
- de Dios, B. V. (2016, January 1). Building and Sustaining National ICT/Education Agencies: Lessons from the Philippines. Building and Sustaining National ICT/Education Agencies: Lessons from the Philippines. Retrieved September 23, 2022, from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/26262>
- Department of Education. (2010, June 10). In DO 78, s. 2010 – Guidelines on the Implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) (p. 1). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2010/06/10/do-78-s-2010-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-the-deped>
- Falqueza, A. (2019, January 18). Utilization of ICT in Improving the Academic Performance of the Grade VI Pupils in Filipino at San Juan West Central School. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*. Retrieved December 14, 2022, from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/7739>
- Goldhaber, A. B., Khuan, H., & Allysa, R. (2021, October 4). Impact of ICT Integration on Quality of Education among Secondary Schools in the USA. *Journal of Education*, 4(6), 6. <https://doi.org/10.53819/81018102t5015>
- Irmayani, N. R., Habibullah, H., Mujiyadi, B., Nurhayu, N., & Erwinsyah, R. G. (2022, October 19). Utilization of ICT in Maintaining Social Resilience in Rural Indonesia. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xpl/Conhome/9915021/Proceeding>, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICISS55894.2022.9915132>
- Jegede, D. (2020, November 19). Challenges Facing the Administration of ICT Infrastructural Facilities in Public Primary Schools in Nigeria. *Challenges Facing the Administration of ICT Infrastructural Facilities in Public Primary Schools in Nigeria* by Deborah Jegede
- Masegenya, S., & Mwila, P. (2023, March 2). Information and Communication Technology Usage in Record Keeping in Public Secondary Schools in Ilemela Municipality, Tanzania | *International Journal of Information Systems and Informatics*. <https://doi.org/10.47747/ijisi.v4i1.1058>
- Merillo, J., & Domingo, P. (2019, September 10). Technology in Pedagogy: Teachers' Perception Towards the Effectiveness of ICT Integration in Language Teaching. *Technology in Pedagogy: Teachers' Perception Towards the Effectiveness of ICT Integration in Language Teaching* by Jonathan Merillo, Precious Domingo: SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3442432>
- Murithi, J., & Yoo, J. E. (2021, August 23). Teachers' use of ICT in implementing the competency-based curriculum in Kenyan public primary schools - *Innovation and Education*. *BioMed Central*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42862-021-00012-0>
- Osiesi, M. P., Oke, C. C., Busiyi, A. O., Arulebe, A. L., Okorie, N. C., & Okoh, O. M. (2022). Assessment of Teachers' Perception of the Provision, Use, and Maintenance of Information and Communication Technology Facilities (ICT) in Ekiti State Primary School Libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Phutela, N., & Dwivedi, S. (2019, May 20). Impact of ICT in Education: Students' Perspective. https://papers.ssrn.com/Sol3/Papers.Cfm?Abstract_id=3377617. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3377617>
- Saprikis, V., Anastasia, K., & Charitoudi, G. (2019, November). The Impact of ICT Training on Teachers' Perceptions and Use of the Technology in Education: A case of Greece. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/33730690>
- Tomaro, Q. P. V., & Mutiarin, D. (2018, November 30). ICT Integration in the Educational System of Philippines. In *ICT integration in the educational system of Philippines | Tomaro | Journal of Governance and Public Policy* (pp. 277–278). *Journal of Governance and Public Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.18196/jgpp.5399>
- Xu, W., & Zammit, K. (2020, January 1). Applying Thematic Analysis to Education: A Hybrid Approach to Interpreting Data in Practitioner Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19, 160940692091881. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920918810>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Nel Rusty T. Tamayo

Alejandra B. Tambago High School

Department of Education – Philippines